

SOME ASPECTS OF FORMING A HEALTHY LIFESTYLE FOR STUDENTS

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ABSTRACT

The article presents a study aimed at studying the lifestyle of medical students: their social portrait, food preferences, their living conditions, how medical students find ways out of stress, their opinions about a healthy lifestyle. Issues related to physical activity, sports, hardening among medical students are also disclosed in this article.

Relevance. Health is the first and most important human need, which determines his ability to work and ensures the harmonious development of the individual. It is the most important prerequisite for the knowledge of the surrounding world, for self-affirmation and human happiness. An active long life is an important component of the human factor.

High-quality professional training of students at the university is impossible without their active educational, labor, cognitive activity. Economic and social reasons, which do not allow to increase the period of study, force it to be intensified, which requires students to mobilize their will, psychophysical, spiritual and physical strength. However, today it is unrealistic to raise the question of limiting the increasing tension in the learning process. And, if it is impossible to completely free a student from psycho-emotional and physical stress, then it is necessary to increase the resistance of the body's adaptive

mechanisms to emotional stress and streamline their learning activities. It is necessary to teach students a healthy lifestyle, which is characterized by the unity and expediency of the processes of self-organization and self-discipline, self-regulation and self-development, aimed at the full realization of their essential forces, talents and abilities. A healthy lifestyle is a lifestyle based on the principles of morality, rationally organized, active, labor, hardening and, at the same time, protecting from the adverse effects of the environment, allowing you to maintain moral, mental and physical health until old age.

One of the components of a healthy lifestyle is physical culture and sports. Physical culture is a part of culture, which is a set of values and knowledge created and used by society for the purpose of physical and intellectual development of a person's abilities, improvement of his motor activity and formation of a healthy lifestyle, social

adaptation through physical education, physical training and physical development. The purpose of physical education is the formation of the physical culture of the individual, that is, that side of the general culture of a person that helps to realize his biological and spiritual potential. Physical education begins from the very first days after the birth of a person. Physical education in unity with mental, moral, aesthetic and labor education ensures the comprehensive development of the individual.

The problem of forming a healthy lifestyle has always been relevant. Protecting one's own health is the direct responsibility of each person and he has no right to shift this responsibility to others. Of particular importance for society is the health of young people, including students. The health potential of a future specialist is as important as his special training and professional qualities.

Purpose of the study. The purpose of our work is to study the principles of a healthy lifestyle among students and the ways of its implementation and formation.

Materials and methods. The study is based on the analysis of materials from an anonymous survey of 6th year graduate students of the pediatric and medical faculties of the Samarkand State Medical Institute. In total, 120 students of one stream (12 groups) were interviewed. The questionnaire included more than 20 questions characterizing the student's social status (gender, age, marital status, place of residence), self-assessment of health and lifestyle, their diet and daily routine, as well as physical activity.

Results. The age of the respondents ranged from 23 to 30 years. Most of the respondents were 25 years old. The gender

composition is uneven: 49 girls (41%) and 71 guys (59%). The share of those who are married was 61 (51%), the rest, respectively, 59 (49%). Most students live in student hostels 74 (62%), in their own apartments 24 (20%) and rented 22 (18%). To the question: do you observe the daily regimen, 77 (64%) answered positively, 33 (36%) answered negatively, 74 (62%) of the respondents observe the diet, the remaining 46 (38%), respectively, do not comply. Three meals a day for the majority of respondents - 49 (41%), four meals a day - for 37 (31%), and depending on the circumstances - for 34 (28%). From food, students prefer hot dishes, as well as "FastFood", a small part of students consume dairy products, salads, fruits and cereals. Subjectively, 108 (90%) feel healthy, the rest consider themselves sick 12 (10%). A third of the respondents smoke, drink alcohol more than half of the respondents. Only 2/3 of the students go in for sports. Most of the respondents 51% believe that they follow a healthy lifestyle, 49%, respectively, do not. When asked what ways you use to get out of stress, the following were named: going out into nature, listening to relaxing music, reading books, playing sports, talking with friends and relatives, meditation, distraction with work. Respondents believe that the main reasons for engaging in an unhealthy lifestyle are irresponsible attitude to their own health, the influence of others, lack of willpower, poor education, low culture and low material level. Students receive information on a healthy lifestyle from medical professionals, reading relevant literature, television, in the classroom at the institute, from the Internet and radio. In order for students to lead a healthy lifestyle, according to the respondents'

answers, it is necessary to extend physical education until the end of their studies at the institute, focus on educational work, improve culture, rational distribution of time, increase scholarships, since maintaining and increasing health is an expensive business.

Conclusions. The analysis of the survey shows that the formation of a healthy lifestyle should be started in the family, continued at school and college, be active and stay healthy as long as possible. We believe that it is necessary to introduce into the educational process knowledge aimed at the formation of a healthy lifestyle of student youth, encourage students to maintain and promote health and maintain a healthy lifestyle culture. 6th year students are almost doctors, they themselves should be the standard of health for others, be carriers of information about a healthy lifestyle and actively

promote it among the population. We believe that the following conditions will contribute to solving the problem of preserving the health of students: creating an educational environment in educational institutions that instills valeological literacy; physical education aimed at improving the culture of health and teaching self-control skills; formation of an active position towards one's health and a sustainable interest in a healthy lifestyle. No matter how perfect medicine is, it cannot rid everyone of all diseases. A person is the creator of his own health, for which he must fight. From an early age, it is necessary to lead an active lifestyle, to achieve genuine harmony of health in reasonable ways. It is better to go through life with a bright smile than with a grimace of pain or a disgruntled face. Healthy living habits should become as essential to you as air, water, food.

References:

1. Parvina N. Sh. Promotion of a healthy lifestyle among the population // Economics and Society. - 2022. - No 1(92). - P. 151-157.
2. Hakimovna X. X. et al. PUBLIC HEALTH REFORMS IN THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN //European Journal of Molecular and Clinical Medicine. – 2021. – Т. 8. – №. 2. – С. 820-827.
3. Kushmatova D. E., Khakimova H. K. CURRENT PERSPECTIVES ON THE SUBJECT OF PUBLIC HEALTH AND HEALTH CARE //World Bulletin of Public Health. – 2022. – Т. 6. – С. 51-53.
4. Кушматова Д. Э. ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ В ПЕРИОД ПАНДЕМИИ COVID-19 //БАРҚАРОРЛИК ВА ЕТАКЧИ ТАДҚИҚОТЛАР ОНЛАЙН ИЛМИЙ ЖУРНАЛИ. – 2022. – С. 382-384.
5. Ergashevna K. D. et al. The Level and Structure of the Incidence of Malignant Tumors of the Oral Cavity Among the Population of the Republic of Uzbekistan //International Journal on Integrated Education. – Т. 3. – №. 12. – С. 177-180.
6. Ra A. et al. INVESTIGATE SOIL CONTAMINATION WITH HEAVY METALS WHILE COMMUNITY HEALTH //Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal. – 2022. – Т. 3. – №. 4. – С. 1358-1363.
7. Сулейманов С. Ф., Кушматова Д. Э., Сулейманова Г. С. Отдельные аспекты изучения предмета микробиологии в медицинском вузе //Современное состояние медицинского образования, проблемы и перспективы: материалы третьей Международной учебной онлайн конференции, г. Бухара. – 2020. – Т. 12. – С. 77-79.